

A brief account on radiation chemical studies of antioxidants : Examples from natural phenols, sulfur and selenium compounds[†]

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Abstract : Reactive oxygen species (ROS) is a collective term used for a group of oxidants, which are either free radicals or molecular species capable of generating free radicals. Excessive production of ROS in living cells is a pathological condition known as oxidative stress. These species, depending on their reactivity and oxidizing ability, participate in a variety of chemical reactions and their reactions often cause irreversible chemical changes in biomolecules. Antioxidants are employed to protect the biomolecules from the damaging effects of such free radicals, primarily by their direct reaction. Although free radical reactions involving ROS with antioxidants are studied by several indirect methods, their direct monitoring is possible only by employing fast kinetic methods. Radiation chemistry of aqueous solutions and pulse radiolysis technique in particular has been found to be well suited to probe such reactions. Thus in this article, contributions from radiation chemistry section of BARC on the reactions of biologically important free radicals involved in oxidative stress with antioxidants have been discussed. Reactions of such radicals with curcumin, an antioxidant from turmeric, which was studied extensively in this laboratory using pulse radiolysis technique, has also been presented. In the last three decades, the section has contributed significantly to the understanding of sulfur and selenium based antioxidants. A few recent highlights on these systems using pulse radiolysis have also been compared.

Keywords : Radiation, antioxidant, selenium compounds, sulfur.

Free radicals, oxidative stress and antioxidants

Intracellular production of free radicals is mediated through superoxide ($O_2^{\bullet-}$) radicals and nitric oxide (NO^{\bullet}) radical. Under normal physiologic conditions, nearly 2% of the oxygen consumed by the body is converted into $O_2^{\bullet-}$ during processes like mitochondrial respiration, phagocytosis etc.¹. Its percentage increases under circumstances such as in competitive sports, infections and during exposure to pollutants, UV light, ionizing radiation, etc. NO^{\bullet} , is produced from L-arginine by the three isoforms of nitric oxide synthase (NOS) enzymes¹. Both NO^{\bullet} and $O_2^{\bullet-}$ radicals, are not strong redox agents, but they are converted to powerful oxidizing free radicals like hydroxyl radical ($^{\bullet}OH$), peroxy radicals (ROO^{\bullet}), alkoxy radicals (RO^{\bullet}), singlet oxygen (1O_2), etc. by complex transformation reactions. Some of the radical species are converted to molecular oxidants like hydrogen

peroxide (H_2O_2), peroxy nitrite ($ONOO^-$), hypochlorous acid ($HOCl$), etc. Sometimes these molecular species act as sources of free radicals. For example, H_2O_2 is converted to $^{\bullet}OH$ radicals by Fenton reaction in the presence of trace metals and $HOCl$ can be converted to 1O_2 . $ONOO^-$, at physiologic pH is in equilibrium with the protonated form peroxy nitrous acid ($ONOOH$), which reacts with substrates through $^{\bullet}OH$ radical and nitrogen dioxide (NO_2^{\bullet}) radical and at physiological concentrations of carbon dioxide, it becomes a source of carbonate radical anion ($CO_3^{\bullet-}$)¹. Different pathways leading to the conversion of NO and $O_2^{\bullet-}$ to other types of reactive free radicals are given in Scheme 1.

Free radicals like $^{\bullet}OH$ radicals, when react with cellular organelles like lipid, protein, DNA, produce different types of secondary radicals like lipid radicals, sugar and base derived radicals, amino acid radicals, thyl radi-

[†]In honour of Professor Jai P. Mittal.

Scheme 1. Reactions leading to the intracellular formation of reactive oxygen species.

icals, etc. These radicals in presence of oxygen are converted to peroxy radicals. Peroxy radicals are critical in biosystems, as they often induce chain reactions¹.

Free radical induced chemical reactions inside the cells are quite complex and the outcome of such reactions depends on several factors like site of generation, nature and type of the cell, expression of redox proteins, activation of repair mechanisms and many more²⁻⁴. For example, free radical reactions with membrane lipids cause lipid peroxidation, which leads to changes in membrane fluidity and structure. Free radical reactions with proteins can lead to their denaturation and loss of vital enzyme activity. Free radical reactions with DNA induce sugar and base modification, causing single and double strand breaks and mutations. Under normal conditions, most of the free radical mediated changes in biomolecules are reversed by the repair mechanisms, but under pathological conditions, the damage may become irreversible and lead to a disease. When less reactive free radicals (less powerful oxidants) are converted to more reactive species inside the cells, there is a shift from reducing status to oxidative status. This shift towards oxidative environment is called **oxidative stress**, which has been implicated in many diseases such as atherosclerosis, cancer, etc. in humans⁵. Cells can overcome small perturbations in oxidative status and regain their original status by antioxidants. **Antioxidants** are compounds that when

present in low concentrations significantly prevent or delay oxidation of the bulk oxidizable substrate. The endogenous antioxidant systems comprise of superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase, glutathione peroxidase and low molecular weight antioxidants like ascorbate, tocopherols, reduced coenzyme, urate, glutathione, etc. These systems either prevent the production of free radicals or inhibit free radical mediated damage to biomolecules or they repair the damaged biomolecule. When the endogenous defense fails, cells need to be supplemented with exogenous antioxidants^{5,6}.

Antioxidants can be classified in many different types. Depending on the solubility and polarity they are either lipid soluble or water-soluble antioxidants. Vitamin E is an example of lipid soluble antioxidants and vitamin C or ascorbic acid is an example of water soluble antioxidant. Vitamins, flavonoids, carotenoids, plant polyphenols etc. are natural antioxidants. Depending on the mechanism of action, antioxidants are classified as preventive and chain breaking antioxidants. Preventive antioxidants, like desferrioximine are compounds; which form chelates with transition metals, thereby help in preventing the free radical production. Radical scavenging antioxidants are the most important class of antioxidants^{5,6}. Ascorbic acid, being a water soluble compound can scavenge •OH radicals that are produced in the cytosol, but lipid soluble compounds like vitamin E, curcumin etc. scavenge chain propagating peroxy radicals therefore these compounds are also termed as chain breaking antioxidants⁷. Vitamin E is one of the first reported lipid soluble chain breaking antioxidants, which is often considered as a standard to compare antioxidant capacity of new molecules. Antioxidants like ascorbic acid help in recycling chain-breaking antioxidants⁸.

In the last two decades there has been a substantial progress in the understanding of reactions of biologically relevant free radicals, and development of new antioxidants, both by biochemical studies and also by monitoring their free radical scavenging abilities. Fast reaction kinetic techniques have been found to be very useful in directly probing the reactions of antioxidants with free radicals having short lifetimes (few microseconds to seconds). Radiation chemical methods, including radiolysis of aqueous solutions and pulse radiolysis technique had made significant contributions to these fields, which are discussed briefly below.

Radiation chemical methods to generate ROS

Since the last half century, radiation chemists have contributed significantly to the understanding of fundamental biological processes and thousands of research papers were published in the literature in the interfacial research areas of chemistry and biology. Radiolysis of water was the common interlink between these two branches of sciences, as living cells contain nearly 70% of water and radiation-induced chemical changes being non-specific cause radiolysis of water. Decades of research by the radiation chemists have led to the complete understanding of the primary radiolytic processes in water. This also provided a unique method to generate almost all the ROS exclusively and study their reactions with antioxidants. They are mentioned briefly here.

Interaction of ionizing radiation with dilute aqueous solutions causes initial excitation and ionization of water molecules, followed by ion-molecule reactions, dissociation reactions, solvation reactions, spur expansion reactions, etc. and at $\sim 10^{-7}$ s after initial interaction of ionizing radiation, the species present in a homogeneous distribution during the radiolysis of water can be represented by the eq. (1)⁹.

Out of these radical species H^{\bullet} and e^-_{aq} are reducing in nature, while $\text{}^{\bullet}\text{OH}$ radicals are oxidizing in nature. Employing suitable additives, such as inorganic salts and dissolved gases, it is possible to convert these primary radicals of water radiolysis to new radicals. With the development of pulse radiolysis technique, it was possible to monitor the free radical reactions with antioxidants in real time scales. The technique utilizes short pulses of charged particles and high-energy photons from accelerators. These short pulses of electrons/charged particles or photons induce a non-equilibrium situation in a small reaction zone in a very short time scale, such that a sufficiently high concentration of transient free radical species is formed. These free radical species are detected within their short lifetimes, by following changes in spectroscopic properties, electrochemical properties or changes in spin density. Although modern pulse radiolysis techniques are capable of producing much shorter pulses ($< 10^{-12}$ s), most of the relevant studies with antioxi-

dants have been performed in the time scale of nanoseconds to a few seconds¹⁰. A block diagram of the pulse radiolysis facility with absorption detection is given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of pulse radiolysis with absorption detection.

$\text{}^{\bullet}\text{OH}$ radicals are important primary radicals produced by radiolysis that are converted to secondary radicals by the additives. Other important oxygen radicals that are commonly employed in antioxidant research are $\text{O}_2^{\bullet-}$ radicals and peroxy radicals. Scheme 2 depicts the reactions involved in the generation of different types reactive oxygen free radicals by radiation chemical methods.

Although many different types of peroxy radicals can be generated by radiation chemical methods¹¹, the most commonly used ones are linoleic acid peroxy (LOO^{\bullet}) radicals¹², methyl peroxy ($\text{CH}_3\text{OO}^{\bullet}$) radicals¹³, trichloromethyl peroxy ($\text{CCl}_3\text{OO}^{\bullet}$)¹⁴ and thiyl peroxy radicals (RSOO^{\bullet})¹⁵. In addition to these, radicals derived from aminoacids are employed to model the reactions involved in the protection of proteins by antioxidants. The most commonly employed aromatic amino acid radicals in radiation chemical experiments are the indolyl radicals of tryptophan (TRP^{\bullet}), and the tyrosine phenoxyl radicals (TYRO^{\bullet}) and sulfur centered radicals from amino acids like histidine, methionine, glutathione (GSH), etc. To evaluate the ability of an antioxidant to protect DNA from oxidative damage, studies on the repair and electron transfer reactions of several antioxidants have been carried out using pulse radiolysis with secondary DNA radicals such as hydroxyl radical adducts of deoxyguanosine monophosphate (dGMP-OH^{\bullet}), deoxyadenosine monophosphate (dAMP-OH^{\bullet}), polyadenylic acid ($\text{poly A-OH}^{\bullet}$), polyguanylic acid ($\text{poly G-OH}^{\bullet}$), single or double stranded DNA (DNA-OH^{\bullet}) and radical anions of thymine ($\text{T}^{\bullet-}$) and thymidine monophosphate ($\text{TMP}^{\bullet-}$), radical cations of dGMP and dAMP ($\text{dGMP}^{\bullet+}$ and $\text{dAMP}^{\bullet+}$)^{11,16,17}

Scheme 2. Generation of reactive oxygen species by pulse radiolysis.

Pulse radiolysis studies of antioxidants : Contributions from BARC

In the last one and half decades, Radiation Chemistry Section of the Chemistry Group, BARC has contributed significantly to the research on antioxidants. A number of phenols, non-phenol compounds have been evaluated for free radical scavenging activity using pulse radiolysis. Natural phenols like, curcumin, folic acid, eugenol, isoeugenol, dehydrogingerone, resveratrol, embelin, sesamol, bergenin, ferulic acid, caffeic acid, cinnamic acid, plumbagin, bakuchiol, ellagic acid, vanillin, Capsaicin, etc. have been studied¹⁸⁻³⁵. The studies were useful in identifying the most favorable site of free radical attack in the phenols and also the factors contributing to the stabilization phenoxyl radicals. Based on these studies, new derivatives with additional and specific properties have been synthesized.

Plant extracts and herbal formulations enriched with phenols have been evaluated for free radical reactions, *in vitro* and *in vivo* activities. Extracts of plant products like *Phyllanthus amarus* Linn., *Phyllanthus emblica* (amla), *Trigonella foenum graecum*, *Plumbago zeylanica*, *Momardica charantia* Linn., *Glycyrrhiza glabra*, *Acacia catechu*, *Terminalia chebula*, *Terminalia arjuna*, *Cysalpinea digyna*, etc.^{22,36-43} have been examined for antioxidant activity. Most of the studies, when correlated with their

biological activity confirmed that free radical scavenging kinetics is one of the main factors controlling their antioxidant activity²². Although these preliminary studies in this direction are very encouraging, due to complexity of formulations and involvement of mixtures of components, these studies have remained only as screening techniques rather than for evaluating the reaction mechanisms. Since it is not possible to discuss the complete research work carried out in BARC, antioxidant and free radical reactions of curcumin, a polyphenol from turmeric has been discussed in detail.

Curcumin

Turmeric is the root of the perennial herb *Curcuma longa*, belonging to the ginger family cultivated in tropical regions of south and southeast Asia. It is commonly used as a spice and coloring agent in Indian cooking. It is a household medicine widely used to cure biliary disorders, anorexia, cough, diabetic wounds, hepatic disorders, rheumatism and sinusitis. The most active component of turmeric is curcumin, which makes upto 2-5% of the spice. Recent scientific research has shown curcumin to be a potent antioxidant with its activity 10 times more than that of the well-known antioxidant vitamin E. It is also an effective anti-tumor agent and is being used in the treatment of almost all types of cancers. It is pharmacologically safe and some clinical reports indicate that hu-

man beings can tolerate a dose of curcumin as high as 8 g/day with no side effects⁴⁴.

The antioxidant potential of curcumin has been confirmed under several *in vitro* conditions, where free radicals are generated. Therefore to understand the free radical reactions between curcumin and ROS, reactions of superoxide radicals, CCl₃OO[•] radicals, lipidperoxy, methyl and methyl peroxy radicals, glutathione radicals, tryptophan radicals, etc. with curcumin have been evaluated using pulse radiolysis and other fast reaction techniques^{44,45}. The rate constants for these reactions determined in aqueous/aqueous-organic solutions are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Rate constants for the reaction of different radicals with curcumin*

Radical	Medium	Rate constant (M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
N ₃ [•]	10% Acetonitrile-water	3.4 × 10 ⁹
CCl ₃ O ₂ [•]	48% Isopropanol-4% CCl ₄ -water	1.2 × 10 ⁸
LOO [•]	Aqueous linoleic acid micelles	7.3 × 10 ⁵
O ₂ ^{•-}	Aqueous TX-100 micelles	4.6 × 10 ⁴
GS [•]	50% Methanol-water	1.0 × 10 ⁸
TRPO [•] radical	Lysozymes-water	5.0 × 10 ⁸
¹ O ₂	Acetonitrile	1.3 × 10 ⁶
CH ₃ [•] radical	40% DMSO-water	3.5 × 10 ⁹
<i>t</i> -Butoxyl radical	Acetonitrile	7.5 × 10 ⁹

In all these reactions, a transient having a lifetime of a few hundred microseconds absorbing from 250 to 600 nm with maximum absorption at 500 nm and extinction coefficient of ~7300 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹ was characterized. In aqueous solutions, the radicals of curcumin decay by second order kinetics with 2k values of 7.5 × 10⁸ M⁻¹ s⁻¹, by radical-radical recombination leading to the formation of products like, vanillin, ferulic acid etc.^{33,34}. In model membrane systems and proteins, the lifetime of curcumin radicals increased by an order of magnitude. Therefore the radicals once generated inside the cells may have long lifetimes and they can be regenerated back to the parent by water-soluble antioxidants like ascorbic acid. The decay kinetics of the radicals of curcumin remained unaffected in presence of oxygen and the absorption spectrum did not change in pH range from 3 to 10, indicating that the observed transient of curcumin is an oxygen centered

phenoxy type radical⁴⁵. Phenoxy radicals are formed either by direct hydrogen abstraction or by initial electron transfer to the free radical, where by a radical cation is formed, which subsequently undergoes a proton loss to produce a phenoxy radical, having resonance stability over the extended conjugation system.

Some reports indicated that the preferred site of free radical reaction in curcumin is the methylenic (CH₂) group and not the phenolic -OH group. To resolve this, our group made a systematic comparison of the antioxidant activity and the free radical reactions of curcumin and dimethoxy curcumin, in which the two phenolic -OH groups were blocked by the alkylation and the diketone moiety is intact. The two compounds were compared for *in vitro* antioxidant activity to inhibit free radical induced lipid peroxidation and hydrogen abstraction reaction with DPPH radicals. The experimental results indicated that curcumin exhibits three times more efficacy in inhibiting lipid peroxidation, and >1000 times more reactive towards DPPH radical when compared to the dimethoxy derivative. Pulse radiolysis induced one-electron oxidation of dimethoxy derivative did not produce the characteristic 500 nm absorbing transient as observed with curcumin. Instead a weak band absorbing at 310 nm, decaying in less than few microseconds was observed. All these studies confirmed that the phenolic -OH makes major contribution in both free radical scavenging activity and hydrogen abstraction reactivity, while the methylenic group makes minor contribution for this and the 500 nm band observed in microseconds during one-electron oxidation corresponds to the phenoxy radical. This was further confirmed by quantum chemical calculations, where the bond dissociation energies of the phenolic -OH and the methylenic (CH₂) group in the diketo form were estimated and found that the O-H bond dissociation energy of the phenolic group is 6.5 kcal/mol lower than the C-H bond dissociation energy of the central CH₂ of the diketo curcumin, suggesting that the phenolic -OH is the most vulnerable target for free radicals in curcumin^{44,46}. All these possible reactions are summarized in Scheme 3. Finally studies on *in vitro* and *in vivo* antioxidant activity of structural and substituted analogues of curcumin suggested that the curcumin derivatives having phenolic -OH can only exhibit efficient antioxidant activity and phenolic -OH is essential for this purpose.

Scheme 3. Different pathways for the formation of curcumin radicals.

These findings have led to convert curcumin to useful products having specific activity derived from the modification of the diketo group. Thus new superoxide dismutase (SOD) enzyme mimics were prepared by chelating the diketo group of curcumin to transition metals like copper and manganese. These compounds retained the free radical scavenging ability and exhibit superior SOD like activity and have been found to show more potent antioxidant ability both *in vitro* and cellular systems⁴⁷.

Studies on sulfur and selenium antioxidants

Sulfur is an essential element for normal physiological functions and sulfur compounds (e.g. thiols) are abundant in cells in the form of aminoacids, proteins, enzymes etc. The nutritional needs of sulfur are met through diet in the form of cheese, milk, garlic, onion, eggs, fruits and cruciferous vegetables^{48,49}. Low molecular weight thiols (RSH) protect cells from oxidative processes and free radical attack. GSH is the major component of intracellular thiols, which is present in millimolar concentrations in mammalian cells, and provides first line of defense for oxidative stress. Sulfur compounds like cysteine, methionine, taurine, glutathione, etc. have been extensively studied as antioxidants. Thiols are indicators of the redox status of cells and the ratio of reduced and oxidized glutathione is used as a marker for oxidative stress.

The protection rendered by thiols (RSH) is conceptualized through a repair mechanism, where they donate hydrogen atom to the damaged target as the S-H bond

energy is less than the C-H bond energy and in biology many of the damaged targets are C-centered. Radiation chemists with the help of pulse radiolysis had provided evidence for this repair process⁵⁰. Thiols, either in free or protein bound form on reaction with free radical oxidants produce thiyl radicals (RS^\bullet)^{17,51,52}. The fate of thiyl radicals inside the cells is a much-discussed topic. The rich chemistry of S-centered radicals and the contributions of pulse radiolysis along with detailed quantum chemical calculations have been compiled in a book edited by Alfassi⁵². The different reactions involved in protection by thiols are given in eqs. (2) to (4).

Unlike sulfur, selenium compounds are much less abundant in nature. The biological importance of selenium has been recognized much recently. It is a constituent of many redox active selenoproteins. Its position between metals and nonmetals makes selenoproteins ideal catalysts for many biological redox transformations. It is an essential micronutrient with a minimum requirement of 55 $\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$, and nutritional supplement of selenium is achieved through diet such as garlic, carrots, cabbage, cheese etc. Selenium deficiency has also been linked with loss of immuno competence and incidence of many diseases. Selenium is a trace mineral, an essential micronutrient and also an active component of the mammalian

selenoprotein^{48,49}. The best characterised and widely studied selenoprotein is glutathione peroxidase (GPx), which is a redox enzyme. GPx is also an antioxidant enzyme and catalyses the reduction of hydroperoxides at the expense of GSH. Because of its catalytic role and ability to undergo easy oxidation, selenium compounds are being explored as new class of antioxidants. The antioxidant mechanism of sulfur and selenium depends on their ability to scavenge ROS, incorporation into proteins, metal binding *etc.*

Pulse radiolysis studies of sulfur and selenium antioxidants

When sulfur and selenium compounds interact with oxidizing radicals, loss of electron occurs from sulfur or selenium centers, producing the respective radicals and radical cations. Unlike the sulfur compounds, the radiation chemistry of selenium compounds is not so much studied and the reactions of selenium centered radicals are not fully understood. Sulfur and selenium centered radicals are unstable and therefore acquire stability by interacting with the near by heteroatoms having lone pair of electrons. Such interactions are greatly influenced by the substituted functional groups and their pKa⁵³. Radiation chemists with the help of pulse radiolysis made extremely useful contributions to the understanding of the sulfur and selenium centered transients and their interactions with heteroatoms. A number of sulfur compounds have been studied at the Radiation Chemistry Section of Bhabha Atomic Research Center (including Dr. J. P. Mittal), employing pulse radiolysis coupled with absorption detection. The nature, and spectral properties of sulfur centred radical cations, radical anions and neutral radicals formed in aromatic and aliphatic thiols, sulfides, disulfides *etc.* have been reported⁵⁴⁻⁵⁸. Wherever possible, quantum chemical calculations have been utilized to explain the experimental observations. Calculations, on stabilization energies, heteroatom interactions transient spectral maxima and secondary chemical reactions have been reported for several sulfur centered radical species. For *e.g.* pulse radiolysis studies of fictionalized thio alkyl compounds (thioalkanol, thioalkanitrile, thioalkanoic acid, -ester, -halides, *etc.*) with varying chain length confirmed the role of inductive effect on the nature of sulfur centered radical cations^{46,47}. Studies on methyl thioacetic acid and its derivatives with [•]OH radical confirmed formation of sulfur centered dimer radical cation via the intermediacy of [•]OH-radical adduct and the formation of

dimer radical cation was found to depend on the electron withdrawing power of the substituted group⁵⁶. Similarly studies on aromatic sulfur compound such as (phenylthio)-acetic acid, diphenyl sulfide, and 4-(methylthio)-phenyl acetic acid, thioanisole, *etc.* showed reaction with [•]OH radical by different channels^{54,55}. The fraction of [•]OH radical reacting to form a solute radical cation was found to increase with increasing concentration of acid, and in highly acidic solutions, the solute radical cation is the only transient species formed on reaction of [•]OH radical with these sulfides^{54,56}. Studies on sulfur compounds having halides, carboxylic and ester functional group showed the formation of sulfur centered radical cation, which was stabilized intramolecularly via donation of the lone pair of electron from the heteroatom. Sulfur compounds with iodide substituent were found to form more stable monomer radical cation as compared to those bearing chloride substituent⁵⁸.

Pulse radiolysis studies with selenium compounds are very limited and recently our group has reported the nature of selenium centered radical cations in many selenium compounds. Selenium centered radical cations formed from compounds like selenourea, selenocystine derivatives, selenomethionine, ebselen and some synthetic selenium compounds have been studied⁵⁹. For *e.g.* selenium centered dimer radical cations of selenourea derivatives and their conversion to elemental selenium have been reported. Further the free radical reactions of nanometer-stabilized selenium have also been studied. Effect of amino and carboxylic acid substitutions on the nature of radical cations in selenocystine derivatives indicated that the acid substitution stabilizes the radical cation, while the amino group induces degradation. It is beyond the scope of this article to compile all the studies on sulfur and selenium compounds carried out in this center. Therefore recent radiation chemical studies on an important amino acid, methionine and its selenium analogue have been discussed below.

Methionine and selenomethionine

Methionine (Met) is an essential aminoacid obtained from the diet and is the primary source of sulfur in the body. It is required for protein synthesis, radical scavenging activity and is considered as an antioxidant⁴⁹. Selenomethionine (SeM) is an important selenium reservoir in plants. SeM is mostly found in plants like garlic, broccoli, onion, *etc.* SeM exhibits glutathione peroxidase

like catalytic activity and has been widely used as an anti-cancer reagent or an antioxidant⁴⁸. Both the compounds showed ROS scavenging ability. Pulse radiolysis was employed to study the reaction of oxidizing radicals like $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals, peroxy radicals with Met and SeM^{60,61}. The stability and reactions of their radical cations were used to compare their relative antioxidant activity.

$\cdot\text{OH}$ radical reacted with both Met and SeM to form radical adducts in which the $\cdot\text{OH}$ radical is attached to either the S or Se atom. These primarily formed radical adducts were converted to radical cations by intramolecular water elimination. The S or Se centered radical cations acquired stability by interaction of the unpaired electron in the p -orbital with the lone pair of electrons in p -orbitals of other atoms like S, Se, N, O, P etc. present either in the same molecule or in another molecule. In Met and SeM, the lone pair in the p -orbital available on N or O can participate in such stabilization, forming (X: \cdot N) or (X: \cdot O) type radical cation, where X is either S or Se. The interaction between positively charged S/Se with the N atom of the amino group would produce a five-member ring structure, while the interaction with negatively charge O atom of the carboxylate group produces six member ring structure. Based on theoretical and experimental studies, the radical cation structure in both Met and SeM has been attributed to the (X: \cdot N) type structure. Formation of this type of radical from hydroxyl radical adduct occurs by intramolecular water elimination involving the proton from the amino group⁵⁰. In the acidic pH when the lone pair is not available, they dimerise to form dimer radical cations. The absorption maxima of the dimer radicals and (X: \cdot N) type radicals of Met and SeM have been found to be at 480 and 380 nm respectively. Similar radicals were observed during the oxidation by one-electron oxidants.

A significant difference between the radical cations of

Met and SeM is the longer lifetime and secondary reactions. The half-life of $\text{Met}^{\bullet+}$ is at least 300 times less than that of $\text{SeM}^{\bullet+}$. As observed with most of the selenium compounds, SeM is easier to undergo oxidation than Met. For example, SeM reacted with $\text{N}_3\cdot$ radical and the reduction potential of the couple $\text{SeM}^{\bullet+}/\text{SeM}$ was determined to be 1.21 ± 0.05 V vs NHE at pH 7. Under the same conditions, Met did not show any reaction with $\text{N}_3\cdot$ radical. The radical cations also showed significantly different types of reactions. $\text{SeM}^{\bullet+}$ radicals are oxidizing in nature and oxidized ABTS^{2-} with rate constant of $2.5 \pm 0.1 \times 10^8 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Similar reactions with $\text{Met}^{\bullet+}$ could not be reported due to their short lifetime. The spectral, kinetic and redox properties of the radical cations of Met and SeM are given in Table 2.

Both $\text{Met}^{\bullet+}$ and $\text{SeM}^{\bullet+}$ undergo decarboxylation and from the estimation of the liberated CO_2 it has been found that majority of $\text{Met}^{\bullet+}$ undergoes decarboxylation, while $\text{SeM}^{\bullet+}$ gives much lower yield of CO_2 . The enthalpy for decarboxylation of $\text{Met}^{\bullet+}$ and $\text{SeM}^{\bullet+}$ were calculated to be -6.4 and $-2.2 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ respectively. This difference in the reaction enthalpies of the two clearly confirmed that the decarboxylation of $\text{SeM}^{\bullet+}$ is relatively slower than that from $\text{Met}^{\bullet+}$. Subsequent to decarboxylation, $\text{SeM}^{\bullet+}$ and $\text{Met}^{\bullet+}$ are converted to 3-methyl-selenopropyl amino radicals and 3-methyl-thiopropyl amino radicals respectively. The 3-methyl-selenopropyl amino radicals are less powerful reducing agents than the 3-methyl-thiopropyl amino radicals. This low reducing ability of the SeM derived α -amino radicals is attributed to the electron releasing nature of selenium atom. All these reactions on Met and SeM have been summarized in Scheme 4.

$\text{SeM}^{\bullet+}$ reacts with molecular oxygen, and the rate constant for this reaction was determined to be $4.3 \pm 0.2 \times 10^8 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Due to the short half life, similar reaction with Met could not be observed experimentally. Because

Table 2. Comparative spectral and other properties of the radical cations formed on one-electron oxidation of methionine (Met) and selenomethionine (SeM)

Physio-chemical parameters	Met (X = S)	SeM (X = Se)
Transient λ_{max} , nm	380 nm (Monomer) 480 nm (Dimer)	380 nm (Monomer) 480 nm (Dimer)
Rate constant for decay of radical cation at pH 7	$3.2 \times 10^6 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$1.1 \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$
$t_{1/2}$ for $>\text{X}:\cdot\text{N}$ - radical	200 ns	70 μs
Equilibrium constant for dimer radical cation formation ($>\text{X}:\cdot\text{X}<$)	$1.9 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$	$9.1 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$
Yield of decarboxylation from radical cation at pH 7	85%	40%
Anodic peak potential by cyclic voltammetry (vs NHE)	1.21 V	0.847 V

Scheme 4. Different possible reactions of hydroxyl radicals with Met and SeM.

of this, SeM^{*+} is converted to selenoxide while Met^{*+} is not easily converted to the sulfoxide. This reaction in particular makes SeM a better antioxidant than Met as the selenoxide can be easily reduced back to SeM by GSH and this reaction does not require the reductase enzyme. Based on this reaction, it is proposed that SeM could provide an important line of defense against oxidative damage in proteins.

Conclusions

Radiation chemistry with the help of pulse radiolysis has been found to be extremely powerful in understanding the free radical reactions of antioxidants in real time scales. Kinetic and thermodynamic properties of antioxidants, determined from such studies provided useful information to predict the feasibility of the radical scavenging ability, one of the essential features of an antioxidant. The studies were also useful to predict the site of free radical attack on the antioxidant molecules and the subsequent reactions of antioxidants. Estimation of one-electron reduction potential of antioxidants, using pulse radiolysis technique was crucial for understanding the fate of the primary and secondary free radical electron reactions. Such studies at molecular level, formed basis for the design of new leads.

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